

Antimicrobial study of polymeric ligands derived from 2, 4-dihydroxy acetophenone and their lanthanide (III) polychelates

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ABSTRACT

In the present work, antimicrobial activities of five polymeric ligands derived from 2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone (DHAP-ED, DHAP-1,2 PD, DHAP-1,3 PD, DHAP-1,3 BD and DHAP-1,4 BD) and its polychelates with La³⁺, Pr³⁺, Nd³⁺, Sm³⁺, Gd³⁺, Tb³⁺ and Dy³⁺ have been studied. Agar diffusion method has been used to determine antimicrobial activity, and the organisms used were *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* (bacteria) and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (yeast). Some important aspects viz. effect of pH, size of inoculums, and choice and ingredient of culture media were also taken into consideration while assessing the antimicrobial activities. From the results it was indicated that the polychelates possess higher antimicrobial activity compared to polymeric ligands primarily due to sharing of electron and increased lipophilicity of the polychelates.

Keywords: Phenolic ligands; 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone; Antimicrobial study; Polychelates; Lanthanides.

INTRODUCTION

Bacteria are both valuable and detrimental to environment, animals and humans. However, many bacteria are pathogens. Diseases such as tetanus, typhoid fever, pneumonia, food-borne illness, leprosy, tuberculosis etc. in humans, while in plants, leaf spot, wilts and fire blight in plants are detrimental effects of bacteria. Bacteria may be found on top of mountains, at the bottom of deepest oceans, in the guts of animal, in the frozen rocks and ice of Antarctica. One feature that has enabled them to spread so far and so long is their ability to go dormant for extended period. The study of the antimicrobial activity of lanthanides and their coordination polymers has great significance, because there are many biological and clinical aspects of coordination compounds of lanthanide (III) ions [1]. The biological properties of the lanthanides based on their similarity to calcium, have stimulated research into their therapeutic applications. Contamination by microorganisms is of great concern in several areas, such as medical devices, health care products, water purification systems, hospitals and dental office equipments, food packaging and food storage in industries etc. One possible way to avoid the microbial contamination is to develop materials possessing antimicrobial activities. Consequently, biocidal polymers have received much attention in recent years [2]. The antimicrobial polymers are suitable in variety of applications such as film and packing

materials, foodstuff, containers, in sanitary applications and many other consumers and common consumer applications like cosmetic, medical equipments and devices.

Literature presents several reports on the use of metal complexes for antimicrobial studies. Cholan et al. [3] have synthesized some transition metal complexes of Co(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II) with Schiff base ligands. The synthesized ligands and their metal complexes were screened for their antimicrobial activity. The activity data showed that the metal complexes to be more potent than the free ligands against one or more bacterial species. Desai et al. [4] prepared some 4-thiazolidinone derivatives and were screened for their antimicrobial activity and antifungal activities at the concentration of 50 mg using DMF as solvent by the agar cup-plate method. The results obtained showed that most of the compounds were moderately active against different strains of bacteria and fungi as compared to standard antibiotics. Most of the compounds were found active against gram negative bacteria but showed better activities against gram positive bacteria.

Ahamad et al. [5] have synthesized poly(ethylene oxamide-N,N'-disuccinate) (PEODS) by condensation of oxamide-N,N'-disuccinic acid and ethylene glycol. Their coordination polymers were synthesized by the reaction of PEODS with hydrated acetates of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II)

and Zn(II). All the synthesized polymers were screened for antibacterial activity against *B. subtilis*, *B. megaterium*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *S. typhi*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. boydii*, and for antifungal activity against *C. albicans*, *T. species*, *A. flavus*, *A. niger*, *F. species*, *M. species* and *P. species* using agar well diffusion methods. Jayakumar et al. [6] synthesized polyurathens containing metal ions in the main chain by reacting hexamethylenediisocyanate or toluene 2,4-diisocyanate with Cu(II), Mn(II) and Zn(II) salts of mono(hydroxyethoxyethyl) phthalate. Mart [7] has synthesized Schiff base oligomer (oligo-ortho-chloroazomethinephenol) by the condensation of ortho-chloroaniline with oligosalicylaldehyde. Oligomer-metal complexes of oligo-ortho-chloroazomethinephenol (OKAP) with Cu(II), Zn(II) and Co(II) were synthesized. Antimicrobial activity of OKAP was tested against *S. cerevisiae*, *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, *M. luteus* and *S. aureus*. Ahamad et al. [8] have carried out in vitro antibacterial and antifungal assay of poly-(ethylene oxamide-N, N'-diacetate) and its polymer-metal complexes.

Coordination polymers are used as biocidal coatings and to prevent growth of microorganisms on surface, e.g. antifouling paints [9]. When organic polymers are used as adhesive coatings and exposed to the atmosphere, they are infected by microorganisms such as bacteria and fungi [10]. Microorganisms have been found to be the cause for disbonding and blistering of protective coatings in various service situations. Coating material itself can be infected by microorganisms from outside and bring about the deterioration in such a way that the physical reactions leading to disbonding and blistering can take place. This problem can be solved by addition of metal ion into polymeric system [11], which changes the physicochemical as well as biological properties of the polymers [12].

In our previous reports, we reported the synthesis and characterization of 2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone derived polymeric ligands (resins) [13], and the catalytic activity of their lanthanum polychelates for Beginelli reactions [14]. In the present study, the synthesized polymeric ligands and their lanthanide (III) polychelates were studied for their antimicrobial activity. Yeast strain *Saccharomyces Cerevisiae* and bacterial strains such as *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus Aureus*, and *Bacillus Subtilis* were used as test bio-organism for the biocidal activity testing.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Chemicals and materials

Dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) solvent was of analytical reagent grade purchased from Central Drug House Pvt. Ltd. (New Delhi, India). AR grade D (+) glucose was procured from E. Merck (Mumbai, India). The hydrated acetate salts of lanthanide ions such as Pr³⁺, Nd³⁺, Sm³⁺, Tb³⁺ and Dy³⁺ were procured from Otto Chemie Pvt. Ltd. (Mumbai, India), while the acetate salts of La³⁺, and Gd³⁺ were purchased from Alpha Chemika (Mumbai, India); all the acetate salts had purity $\geq 99.9\%$. Yeast strain of *Saccharomyces Cerevisiae* was purchased from Mitushi Pharma (Gujarat, India). Bacterial strains viz. *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus Aureus*, *Bacillus Subtilis* were purchased from IMTECH (Chandigarh, India). For the preparation of growth mediums agar, beef extract, malt extract powder, yeast extract and peptone were purchased from Titan Biotech Limited (Rajasthan, India). Deionized water was prepared from Milli Q water purification system from Millipore (Bangalore, India).

Synthesis of polymeric ligands and their Ln(III) polychelates

The detailed synthesis and characterization of all five polymeric ligands, poly [(2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone) ethylene] [DHAP-ED]; poly [(2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone)1,2- propylene] [DHAP-1,2 PD]; poly [(2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone)1,3 propylene] [DHAP-1,3 PD]; poly [(2, 4-dihydroxy acetophenone)1,3-butylene] [DHAP-1,3 BD] and poly [(2, 4-dihydroxy acetophenone)1,4-butylene] [DHAP-1,4 BD] has been reported previously by us [13]. Briefly, to a well stirred ice-cooled mixture of 2, 4-dihydroxyacetophenone and ethandiol /1,2-propanediol/1,3-propanediol/1,3-butanediol/1, 4- butanediol, polyphosphoric acid was added slowly with stirring as a catalyst. The reaction mixture was left at room temperature for half an hour and condensed on an oil bath at 145°C for 10 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, poured on crushed ice and left overnight. The product was collected by filtration and washed with cold water and methanol to remove unreacted acid and monomer. The yield of all the resins ranged from 80-83 %. The structures of synthesized polymeric ligands are given in Figure 1(A-E). For the synthesis of polychelates, a solution of the hydrated lanthanide acetate salts was added with constant stirring to a hot and clear solution of polymeric ligands. The suspension was digested on a water bath for 2 h and then filtered. The blackish-brown colored polychelates obtained were washed, first with cold DMSO and then with acetone, and dried. The yield obtained was in the range of 60-80%. The proposed chemical structure of Ln(III) polychelate of DHAP-ED is shown in Figure 2.

Composition of the medium for bacteria and yeast

Slant preparation: Nutrient agar media dissolved in distilled water and was sterilized by autoclave. About 5 mL of molten media was transferred in previously sterilized test tubes. The test tubes were then plugged tightly and were placed in a slanting position to cool and solidify. Stock culture: The stock culture was grown on nutrient agar slants by incubating for 24 h at 37°C.

Inoculum preparation of bacteria and yeast: Bacterial and Yeast culture, a loop of cell mass from pre-grown slants was inoculated into sterile N-broth tubes containing 15 mL medium and incubated on a shaker at 150 rpm and 37 °C for 24 h to obtain sufficient cell density (i.e. 1×10^8 cells/mL).

Solutions of polymeric ligands and their polychelates: Complexes used in the present study were insoluble in water, but soluble in DMSO. Therefore, to study antibacterial activity of the complexes, their solutions were prepared in DMSO, which does not have any antimicrobial activity.

Preparation of microbial culture and screening of compounds for their antimicrobial activity

The antimicrobial activity of polymeric ligand and its polychelates was checked against *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and Yeast strains *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. The antimicrobial effect of the compounds was investigated by standard microbiological parameters using Agar Diffusion Method [15]. The concentration of the compound tested for the antimicrobial activity was 500 ppm during the experiment. The bacterial culture was maintained on N-agar (N-broth, 2.5% w/v agar). On the other hand, the yeast culture was maintained on MGYP in 3% (w/v) agar. All were sub cultured every fortnight and stored at 0-5 °C; the details are provided as follows;

Nutrient Broth Medium: Beef extract-1.5 g; Peptone-6.0 g; Sodium chloride-1.5 g; Agar-20 g; Distilled water- 1000 mL; pH adjusted to 6.7-7.3.

MGYP (malt extract-glucose-yeast extract-peptone) Medium: Yeast extract-3.0 g; Malt extract-3.0 g; Peptone-3.0 g;

Glucose- 5.0 g; Agar-10 g; Distilled water- 1000 mL; pH adjusted to 5.5.

For inoculums of bacterial and yeast culture, a loop of cell mass from pre-grown slants was inoculated into sterile N-broth tubes containing 15 ml medium and incubated by shaking at 150 rpm and 37 °C for 24 h, to obtain sufficient cell density (1×10^8 cells/mL).

Sterile, melted N-agar was initially inoculated with respective cultures and poured into a sterile empty petri dish and allowed to solidify. A ditch was prepared with the help of a sterile scalpel on

opposite ends, with one for control (solvent without compound) and the other for the test sample. For finding the minimum inhibitory concentration, all the cultures were tested for different concentration of compound ranging from 50-1000 ppm. Thereafter, the plates were transferred to the refrigerator for 10 min to allow the sample diffuse out from the ditch and into the agar before organisms start growing, followed by incubation at 37 °C for 24 h. Next day the distance in millimeter (mm), from the ditch was measured as a parameter of inhibition.

Figure 1 Chemical structure of synthesized polymeric ligands

Figure 2 Proposed chemical structure of Ln(III) polychelate of DHAP-ED (where, M = La(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Tb(III) and Dy(III); X=H₂O)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Antimicrobial activity of polymeric ligands and their polychelates

Various methods have been proposed and adopted for the measurement of antibacterial activity [16], viz. agar streak dilution method, agar diffusion method, turbidometric method, special dilution method, and specific method (specific for measuring the action of specific substance). However, in the present study Agar diffusion method [15] has been used to investigate antimicrobial activity of the synthesized polymer and polychelates.

Antibacterial activity is usually tested by making aqueous solution of the compounds. However, complexes used in the present study were insoluble in water, and hence their solutions were prepared in DMSO. DMSO was inactive towards the selected micro-organisms as demonstrated from blank experiment carried out with DMSO alone and tested thereafter. Therefore, to study antibacterial activity of the complexes, their solutions were prepared in DMSO.

The polymeric ligands and their metal complexes were studied for their antimicrobial activity against standard bacterial strains of *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* (bacteria) and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (yeast). The

compounds were tested at different concentrations ranging from 50-1000 ppm, to find out the minimum concentration of the ligand and polymer-metal complexes, which inhibits the microbial growth. The minimum concentration was found effective was 500 ppm. The inhibition of growth from the ditch was measured in millimeter (mm) and the results are shown in Table 1-5. The polymeric ligands were found biologically active, however, their polymer-metal complexes showed significantly enhanced antibacterial activity against one or more bacterial species, in comparison to their corresponding uncomplexed polymeric ligands. It is known that chelation tends to make the ligands act as more potent bactericidal agents, than the parent ligand.

Antimicrobial activity of polychelates increases significantly because chelation reduces the polarity of the central metal ion, by partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor groups which further leads to the enhancement of complex's lipophilicity [17]. Since the microorganism cell is surrounded by a lipid membrane which favors the passage of lipid soluble materials, increased lipophilicity allows the penetration of complex into and through the membrane and deactivates the active enzyme sites of the microorganisms [18]. Other factors, viz., stability constant, molar conductivity, solubility and magnetic moment are also responsible for increase in the anti-microbial activity of the complexes [19].

Table 1 Antimicrobial activity data of the polymeric ligand (DHAP-ED) and its polychelates

Ligand/Polychelates	Zone of inhibition (mm)			
	<i>E. Coli</i> ^a	<i>B. Subtilis</i> ^b	<i>S. Aureus</i> ^c	<i>S. Cerevisiae</i> ^d
(DHAP-ED) _n	--	--	--	11
([La(DHAP-ED) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	17	21	18	21
([Pr(DHAP-ED) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	18	20	20	20
([Nd(DHAP-ED) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	19	19	21	23
([Sm(DHAP-ED) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	16	20	19	20
([Gd(DHAP-ED) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	18	21	21	21
([Tb(DHAP-ED) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	19	19	20	20
([Dy(DHAP-ED) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	16	22	21	22
DMSO	--	--	--	--

^a *Escherichia coli*; ^b *Bacillus subtilis*; ^c *Staphylococcus aureus*; ^d *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*; DHAP-ED: poly[(2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone)ethylene]; DMSO: Dimethyl sulphoxide

Table 2 Antimicrobial activity data of the polymeric ligand (DHAP-1,2-PD) and its polychelates

Ligand/Polychelates	Zone of inhibition (mm)			
	<i>E. Coli</i> ^a	<i>B. Subtilis</i> ^b	<i>S. Aureus</i> ^c	<i>S. Cerevisiae</i> ^d
(DHAP-1,2-PD) _n	--	--	--	10
([La(DHAP-1,2-PD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	17	20	18	19
([Pr(DHAP-1,2-PD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	18	21	20	21
([Nd(DHAP-1,2-PD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	15	22	19	22
([Sm(DHAP-1,2-PD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	19	19	22	19
([Gd(DHAP-1,2-PD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	15	20	23	23
([Tb(DHAP-1,2-PD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	17	21	20	22
([Dy(DHAP-1,2-PD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	16	22	19	20
DMSO	--	--	--	--

^a *Escherichia coli*; ^b *Bacillus subtilis*; ^c *Staphylococcus aureus*; ^d *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*; DHAP-1,2-PD: poly[(2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone)1,2-propylene]; DMSO: Dimethyl sulphoxide

Table 3 Antimicrobial activity data of the polymeric ligand (DHAP-1,3-PD) and its polychelates

Ligand/Polychelates	Zone of inhibition (mm)			
	<i>E. Coli</i> ^a	<i>B. Subtilis</i> ^b	<i>S. Aureus</i> ^c	<i>S. Cerevisiae</i> ^d
(DHAP-1,3-PD) _n	--	--	--	11
([La(DHAP-1,3-PD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	17	21	20	21
([Pr(DHAP-1,3-PD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	16	20	22	22
([Nd(DHAP-1,3-PD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	15	19	21	21
([Sm(DHAP-1,3-PD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	18	22	19	23
([Gd(DHAP-1,3-PD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	17	21	21	22
([Tb(DHAP-1,3-PD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	16	19	23	20
([Dy(DHAP-1,3-PD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	17	22	22	21
DMSO	--	--	--	--

^a *Escherichia coli*; ^b *Bacillus subtilis*; ^c *Staphylococcus aureus*; ^d *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*; DHAP-1,3-PD: poly[(2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone)1,3-propylene]; DMSO: Dimethyl sulphoxide

Table 4 Antimicrobial activity data of the polymeric ligand (DHAP-1,3-BD) and its polychelates

Ligand/Polychelates	Zone of inhibition (mm)			
	<i>E. Coli</i> ^a	<i>B. Subtilis</i> ^b	<i>S. Aureus</i> ^c	<i>S. Cerevisiae</i> ^d
(DHAP-1,3-BD) _n	--	--	--	11
([La(DHAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	16	20	21	21
([Pr(DHAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	17	21	17	20
([Nd(DHAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	19	22	19	21
([Sm(DHAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	18	21	21	19
([Gd(DHAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	20	19	22	22
([Tb(DHAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	19	20	20	21
([Dy(DHAP-1,3-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	20	23	21	22
DMSO	--	--	--	--

^a *Escherichia coli*; ^b *Bacillus subtilis*; ^c *Staphylococcus aureus*; ^d *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*; DHAP-1,3-BD: poly[(2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone)1,3-butylene]; DMSO: Dimethyl sulphoxide

Table 5 Antimicrobial activity data of the polymeric ligand (DHAP-1,4-BD) and its polychelates.

Ligand/Polychelates	Zone of inhibition (mm)			
	<i>E. Coli</i> ^a	<i>B. Subtilis</i> ^b	<i>S. Aureus</i> ^c	<i>S. Cerevisiae</i> ^d
(DHAP-1,4-BD) _n	--	--	--	10
([La(DHAP-1,4-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	16	20	21	21
([Pr(DHAP-1,4-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	17	21	23	18
([Nd(DHAP-1,4-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	18	22	19	20
([Sm(DHAP-1,4-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	19	19	18	19
([Gd(DHAP-1,4-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	19	20	19	22
([Tb(DHAP-1,4-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	20	22	20	21
([Dy(DHAP-1,4-BD) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]OH) _n	18	21	22	20
DMSO	--	--	--	--

^a *Escherichia coli*; ^b *Bacillus subtilis*; ^c *Staphylococcus aureus*; ^d *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*; DHAP-1,4-BD: poly[(2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone)1,4-butylene; DMSO: Dimethyl sulphoxide

CONCLUSION

The results indicate that all the polychelates of lanthanides (III) with the polymeric ligands show good antimicrobial activity compared to free polymeric ligands. It is found that chelation tends to make the ligands act as more potent bactericidal agents than the parent ligands. The increase in activity is due to the formation of a chelate as the positive charge of the metal is partially shared with the donor atoms of the ligands and there is π -electron delocalization over the whole chelate ring.

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